

Table 1. Participant characteristics

		Psychologists	AHPs/clinicians
		N=34	N=130
		n (%)	n (%)
NHS Trust	Northeast England	1 (2.9)	12 (9.2)
	Northwest England	2 (5.9)	10 (7.6)
	Yorkshire and Humber	0	10 (7.6)
	East Midlands	1 (2.9)	5 (3.8)
	West Midlands	3 (8.8)	11 (8.4)
	East of England	0	8 (6.1)
	London	7 (20.6)	21 (16.0)
	Southeast England	2 (5.9)	10 (7.6)
	Southwest England	9 (26.5)	20 (15.3)
	Scotland	4 (11.8)	10 (8.4)
	Wales	2 (5.9)	6 (4.6)
	Northern Ireland	3 (8.8)	7 (5.3)
Professional Role	Psychologist band 7	3 (8.8)	
	Psychologist band 8a	15 (44.1)	
	Psychologist band 8b	9 (26.5)	
	Psychologist assistant band 4-5	1 (2.9)	
	Nurse		18 (13.7)
	Dietitian		10 (7.6)
	Clinical lead		39 (29.8)
	Hospital Physician		55 (42.0)
	Consultant		1 (0.8)
	Physician associate		1 (0.8)
	Other	6 (17.6)	6 (4.6)
Age of patients seen	Under 16 years only	10 (29.4)	45 (34.6%)
	Under 18 years only	22 (64.7)	40 (30.8)
	16-18 years only	0	2 (1.5)
	Under 18 years and 18+ transitioning to adult care	2 (5.9)	8 (6.2)
	18+ transitioning to adult care and adults	0	5 (3.8)
	Over 16 years and adults	0	18 (13.8)
	Adults only	0	8 (6.2)
	All ages	0	4 (3.1)